

Impact of Availability and Utilization of Printed Media Resources on Teacher's Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper assessed the Impact of Availability and Utilization of Printed Media Resources on Teacher's Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The study established one objective, one research question and formulated one null hypothesis which was subsequently tested for the study. Employing a descriptive survey research design, the population included 19,598 Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students and 361 Economics teachers across 114 Senior Secondary Schools offering Economics in Sokoto State. A sample size of Three hundred and sixty-five (365) was selected for the study. The data collection instrument, "Questionnaire for Economics Teachers and Students (QETS)," was utilized. The reliability coefficient results of 0.85 was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha, in pilot testing the instrument. The analysis involved employing descriptive statistics, such as Mean and Standard Deviation to answer research questions. Meanwhile, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U-Test was applied to test the Null Hypothesis. The results indicated the retaining of the formulated null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05. The study's outcomes underscored the significant impact of availability and utilization of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher delivery in Economics in senior secondary schools in Sokoto State. The study also uncovered that newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State (as indicated by P-value). In conclusion, based on these findings, recommendations were made for the state Ministry of Education, school management, teachers, parents, NGOs, and philanthropies to always make printed media resources available for teachers to use for proper teacher delivery in Economics, additionally, it was also recommended that, the School management should organize relevant workshops, training and re-training of Economics teachers on how to improvise such resources and they should also encourage their students to bring any relevant printed materials to school for use, storage, retrieval, and re-use to enhance effective teacher delivery in Economics in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Keywords: Availability, Utilization, Printed Media, and Resources.

Introduction

Printed media resources that include newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets encompassing publications, documents, records, or any printed media utilized by teachers, play crucial roles in the teaching and learning processes. These materials serve to facilitate instruction and aid in the achievement of lesson objectives. As integral components of the curriculum and learning resources, they contribute meaningfully to the clarity and comprehensiveness of lessons for learners. They enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of teaching and learning by engaging the various senses of students, facilitating the impartation of knowledge, skills, and experiences. They have the capacity to stimulate students' interest, capture their attention, and enrich the teaching and learning process in Economics, thereby imbuing classroom instruction with greater meaning and relevance. They also help teachers achieve curriculum objectives, make lessons explicit to the learners, and choose the best learning experience to be communicated to the learners. Further, the Printed media resources help Economics teachers create conducive learning environments and ease teacher's delivery at various levels of learning, particularly among Secondary Schools (Ahmed, 2019).

The use of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets might solve the problems of poor academic performance among Economics students, negative perception of the subject, and massive failure in WAEC, NECO and JAMB Examinations. This lies in the assessment of these publications, learning experience and lesson objectives by the teachers which can improve teacher delivery. Conversely, poor teacher delivery may bring negative perception of the subject matter, students' failure and poor academic performance. Hence, it necessitates assessing the impact of the availability and utilization of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery. Furthermore, these learning resources are necessary for the handling, management and control of the teaching and learning process. They not only focus the student's attention and interest but also simplify the whole concept, the process of teaching, and teacher's delivery. They also reduce the massive failures of external and internal Economic examinations at all levels. They communicate experiences and encourage active participation of students, whereby learning will be concretized and permanent (Usman, 2016).

Teacher delivery is a channel by which teachers communicate the intended learning experience or subject matters to the learners for effective instructions/delivery. It is crucial and impossible to overstate the importance of using newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets while teaching and learning Economics. This can have an impact on curriculum and students' academic achievement. Based on the researcher's experience, Economics teachers in Sokoto State's Secondary Schools neglected the use of these printed teaching resources when instructing and learning about Economics. Some teachers regard utilizing them as stressful and upsetting. It is lamenting the way Economics teachers show up to class to teach without these printed materials despite being aware of the value of using them in the delivery of teaching. This research was necessary to address this issue as well as others that have not yet been identified to avoid verbalism and inappropriate teacher's delivery in Economics. This also necessitated the need to conduct this study to improve the academic performance of Economics students and open a new page for all the schools in Sokoto state (Idris, 2015)

In order to address the scarcity issues of printed media resources, Economics teachers ought to be able to make them available. Through these initiatives, Economics will be taught and learned in a more tangible and efficient manner, increasing students' comprehension in all ways. All teaching and learning procedures need the use of these printed resources. On the other hands, it is well acknowledged that, the utilization of printed media resources among secondary schools are essential components in fostering students' comprehension and efficient instruction (Bright and Jonathan, 2019). It is important to choose these resources wisely in order to provide students with experiences that are relevant and could boost their academic achievement. When properly utilized, these resources can contribute meaningfully to the proper understanding of topics or lesson contents. This can also make Economics lessons or teaching and learning of Economics very easy and more simplified. Eventually, the findings of this study will stimulate students' interest, increase their academic performance and make learning permanent through effective teacher's delivery and utilization of efficient printed media resources. It will also enhance students' clarification of concepts and ideas in Economics. Students can also materialize learning, which will help them retain more information than usual and improve teacher's delivery in Economics (Isaac and Ikechukwu, 2012) .

What prompted this study were rapid changes in human society and technological advancement, which brought about many changes in almost all human endeavours, including teaching and learning processes in schools. Previous means of teaching are regarded as obsolete due to the fast technological advancement in communication technology. Undoubtedly, the irrelevant and non-utilization of the newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets by Economics teachers may be the major source of students' poor academic performance or massive failures in Economics. Therefore, they need to be assessed using this type of study, which hopes to find the bonds between their impacts and teacher's delivery in Economics. These days, Economics teachers spend less time using and applying relevant newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets in their instructional delivery. A few of these printed publications are hard to find. Teachers cannot supply all of these resources required for instruction in the classroom on their own. Government and other agencies should assist in providing these materials for schools and ensure their effective utilization in any teacher's delivery (Mohammed and Abdullahi, 2019).

Concepts of Economics

Economics is a social science discipline that examines how people produce, distribute exchange, consume, and provide services in order to meet their needs. Economics is a social science since it involves the study of a particular facet of human behaviour, according to Okeke (2005). It is the study of the production, distribution and consumption of wealth (Essien, 2006). However, according to Ande (2018, pp 2), "Economics has no specific definition," but he did provide a few definitions provided by various subject-matter experts. Economics was described by Alfred Marshal as the study of mankind in the ordinary business of life; Adam Smith saw it as an inquiry into the nature and causes of a nation's wealth; and John Stuart Mill saw it as the practical science of production and distribution. According to HJ Davenport, Economics is the science that examines things from a price perspective. Economics is the science of material welfare, according to A.C. Pigou. The definition of Economics advanced by professor (Lord) Lionel C. Robbins is the most inclusive and widely recognised. "As a science which studies

human behaviour as a relationship between ends and scarce means which have alternative uses," is how he described Economics (Anyaele, 2003). Therefore, Economics is social science subject that deals with production and distribution of goods and services to satisfy basic human wants. It also teaches households on how to manage the little resources at their disposal for more satisfaction.

Concepts of Instructional Materials

Instructional Materials are called with different names, such as teaching aids, learning materials, teaching materials, tools, learning resources, instructional resources, instructional media, curriculum resources, learning aids, teaching-learning materials, educational resources, curriculum materials, curriculum media, instructional aids, and teaching resources. The teacher uses materials to facilitate the teaching and learning process or make learning explicit to the learners. The following are some definitions of instructional materials as given by some authors. According to Yusuf (2012, pp181), the teacher uses Curriculum Materials to help students learn. These include books, charts, text, manuals, audio-visual aids, laboratory equipment, artefacts and other archaeological materials". Bara'u (2020) observes that a collection of human and non-human resources that a teacher can utilize in a teaching and learning environment to achieve the intended set objectives in a particular session is called instructional materials or teaching-learning materials (TLM). Further, Igunnu, Aliyu, Hassan and Abdurashed (2015) stated that the resources used in instructional lessons that incorporate evaluation and active learning are called instructional materials. Curriculum resources, according to Danladi (2006), are anything and anybody that a classroom instructor can use to assist both themselves and the students in achieving certain educational objectives. Curriculum materials are representation tools that teachers use to support and guide their teaching practice (Kanno, Obasi and Solomon, 2016). At the same time, Uyagu and Bara'u (2018) opined that resources refer to all things (human and non-human) that are purposefully used to make teaching and learning more meaningful and productive. To this end, Guga (2019) explained that Instructional resources are all materials the teacher uses to facilitate and concretize learning. These materials resources are further classified into tangible and intangible materials. Therefore, teaching resources can be explained as anything the teacher uses to stimulate learning and help pupils (students) appreciate and understand the knowledge, skills, and attitudes learned.

Concepts of Printed Media Resources

Printed media resources are written, textual, printed, and published, as well as reading materials used by Economics teachers in teaching and learning Economics among Secondary Schools. They are also printed or re-printed documents, records, or publications on papers used as a medium of instruction to communicate experiences and knowledge to the learners and make learning permanent, aiding and developing students' memory. They can also be used in individualized, group, mass or class learning. They can be in different forms or formats and can be re-printed, retrieved, duplicated, stored or reproduced for effective teachers' and students' utilization in any classroom instructions. According to Olubunmi (2012), Printed media resources or media include printed materials from which one can obtain information and knowledge and acquire facts, skills, principles and enlightenment. However, Danladi (2006) Printed instructional materials or reading materials refer to daily or weekly newspapers, magazines, periodicals, pamphlets, textbooks, etc. Printed materials included any text and anything else that could be generated in large quantities with a printer or duplicator. Nelyloves (2014) further stated that printed materials refer to any publication, document, or record. Any text and other material that could be produced in large quantities using a printer or duplicator were considered printed materials. Furthermore, to some authors, Printed media resources mean documents or papers that convey information via the written word. Examples of dictionaries, pictures, posters, or printed materials are general books, journals, serials, magazines, newspapers, maps, and atlases (Lawinsider, 2023). Josua (2015) further said that printed materials are any written materials, except non-print resources that provide scheduled course information. Textbooks, workbooks, reference books, periodicals, newspapers, and journals are a few examples. To this end, printed media resources are powerful tools or instructional materials that offer students opportunities to re-read what was taught in the class at ease. They are the best media to be used by Economics teachers in their efforts to make learning explicit and clear to the students.

Concepts of Teacher Delivery

Teacher delivery, otherwise known as teaching delivery, lesson delivery, instructional delivery or learning delivery is a process of presenting a lesson to achieve lesson objectives and effective evaluation. It also involves structuring the learning experience, instructional materials, objectives, and contents so that the teacher will ensure the free flow of lessons, interaction among students and attainment of learning objectives using appropriate instructional materials and effective methodologies. According to Safia (2022), learning delivery are means of imparting knowledge to students. This suggests that to provide the desired learning experience and achieve particular goals, you must use particular technology, resources, and facilities. On the other hand, Insider (2022) asserted that teaching delivery involves various activities, including group instruction, seminars, lectures, tutorials, lab sessions, clinical/practicum sessions, fieldwork, and supervision. According to Lukman (2022), demonstrating each tasks a teacher and student completes in a classroom context is considered instructional delivery. However,

Tangient (2014) also opined that, lesson delivery is all about holding true to the objective of the lesson, engaging the students and appropriate pacing of the lesson based on students' needs. According to Als-Est (2022) teaching/learning delivery comprises means and resources used to structure the learning experience. Teacher or learning delivery has some methods which include face-to-face, virtual learning, online learning, blended learning and mobile learning (Safia, 2022). Therefore, teacher delivery means effective lesson presentation, setting of lesson objectives and contents according to students' interests by engaging them in teaching and utilization of printed media resources with the hope of achieving effective evaluation.

Concept of Secondary School

Secondary schools are learning institutions that offer students secondary education immediately after completing nine years of basic education and before tertiary education. The junior secondary school is today called upper Basic and is part of basic education, while Senior Secondary School is called Post Basic. They can be Day or Boarding schools. According to Stenfy (2023), secondary schools are educational institutions that fall somewhere between elementary and college. They often provide general, technical, vocational, or college preparation courses. According to National Teachers' Institute (2000), secondary school is the type of education provided following primary school but before tertiary education. However, according to Solomon (2023) Secondary School is a form of education which children received automatically after completing their elementary school education. Secondary school is the next step after primary school, according to Shabista (2023). It serves as a link between elementary and high school education. (Epler, 2022). The next level up from primary school is secondary school. It is a school for kids between 11 and 18 (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023). It is ongoing education after the completion of basic education (primary education). Students in secondary schools usually range in age from 9 to 18 (or occasionally a little older). To this end, Secondary School is an academic institution that offers secondary education to children after completion of primary education.

Types of Printed Media Resources.

Printed media resources can be grouped or classified into different forms and types to serve different purposes and functions. Some are printed/published materials, while others are in form of posters that can be used as Printed instructional materials in any teacher delivery in Economics. The following are some of the Printed media resources, as cited in Chakrabarti (2023), Uzmasaniya (2021), Nelyloves (2014) and Taylor (2023) that are usually available and utilized by Economics teachers in any teacher's delivery in Economics at all levels: Newspapers, Magazines, Journals, Articles, Periodicals and Pamphlets

Newspapers: Newspapers are printed papers or documents containing national and international news, current events, articles of opinion, nation economic activities and deliberations, advertisements, businesses, sports, political events, weather forecasts, news stories, information, etc., which are printed, published and distributed daily or weekly. Newspapers are the primary mass media channel for disseminating information, especially in the domains of politics and Economics, claims Drew (2023). On the other hand, School Wikipedia Selection (2007) asserted that a newspaper is a periodical that publishes news, information, and advertisements and is typically produced on inexpensive newsprint paper. It is usually published daily or weekly and might be specific or generic. In order to do this, newspapers in the targeted areas should produce and provide extra supplements to the school to gradually shift their focus to the fundamental concerns of education (Lawinsider, 2023). Therefore, newspapers can be used as sources of information and printed instructional materials by Economics teachers in teaching-learning processes. It can be used to teach topics like the labour market, company among others

Types of Newspaper: There are two types of newspapers: **Daily newspaper** – a type of newspaper issued daily, often except on Sundays and national holidays and **Weekly newspapers** are newspapers that are issued weekly. They are also common, smaller, and less prestigious than daily papers (Drew, 2023). However, newspapers are the most important printed instructional materials for Economics teachers. They can be used to teach topics like budgets and their types, Economic policies, allocation formulas, inflation, deflation, foreign currency prices, exchange markets, etc. Economics teachers can obtain information related to the topics before them. Journalists educate people, including students, on political, social, economic and cultural development. They also provide formal and informal education (Lawinsider, 2023). And can be used as printed instructional materials in teaching and learning Economics

Magazine: A magazine is printed material published every week or month containing stories, essays, pictures, photographs, articles, information, or in short, containing different contents. Drew (2023) stated that magazines are printed periodicals typically released monthly or bi-monthly. They are usually geared towards a specific intended audience and often have a specific focus or niche. However, magazines can be used as printed instructional materials in any teacher's delivery to facilitate instructions and attainment of the lesson objectives. Economics teachers can easily use magazines to teach topics such as production, public companies, etc., for more elaboration.

Journal / Academic Journal: An academic journal is a printed and compiled set of academic write-ups involving research and publications of various academic articles from scholars in different educational fields or disciplines. Experts or

researchers in various subjects or professions wrote it. Academic journals might contain economic, political, social, scientific, cultural and religious matters. It can be used as printed instructional materials in any teacher's delivery to enhance students' understanding of various topics. McKenzie (2017), a journal is a collection of articles (like magazines) published regularly throughout the year. An academic journal is a periodical publication in which scholarship relating to a particular academic discipline is published (Lawinsider, 2023). Economics teachers can use journals to teach certain topics in Economics, such as business organizations, banking and finance, etc.

Article: An article is a piece of writing about a particular subject or discipline usually found in newspapers, magazines, journals, etc., and included in printed or online publications. To Stenfy (2023), an article refers to writing about a particular subject in a magazine, newspaper, etc. Further, Economics teachers can use the articles as print material in any teacher's delivery to make the teaching and learning process lively and explicit to the learners. They are also important in attracting students' attention towards the lesson and learning activities in classrooms in most schools. Article can appear in different forms, such as newspapers, magazines, and academic journals. They can also be used in teaching and learning processes in Economics at all levels of learning.

Periodical: A periodical is also one of the printed instructional materials. It is a booklet, often with illustrations, issued at fixed intervals (or periods), typically once a month or weekly (Drew, 2023). However, Spacey (2020) opined that a periodical is any regular publication such as a monthly, semi-annual or annual journal. Economics teachers can use periodicals in any teacher delivery to make lessons explicit to the learners. Some economic matters can be discussed in detail, allowing teachers to utilize them in their classroom instruction to motivate and arouse students' interest.

Pamphlet: A pamphlet is a small printed or published booklet that contains information about a particular subject, topic or discipline that covers many types of printed and digital materials. It may consist of a single sheet of paper printed on both sides and folded in half, in a third or fourth, called a leaflet, brochure, flyer, hand outs or booklet, and make a simple book. However, according to Nona (2021), a pamphlet is a little book or leaflet that primarily informs or educates readers about a specific topic. These come in several formats, such as tri-fold and single-sheet leaflets. Teachers can use pamphlets as printed instructional materials in any teacher delivery to ease instruction.

The significant challenges of massive failure, poor academic performance, and slow rate of learning in Economics in both internal and external examinations, are likely to be attributable to lack of qualified Economics teachers, unavailability of relevant printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets, poor skills and inexperience in teaching and learning process by Economics teachers, inadequate utilization of printed media resources and teachers' attitude towards it, lack of improvisational skills by Economics teachers or ineffective teacher's delivery. The problems of teaching Economics, especially regarding the use of inappropriate newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets, posed many challenges and problems to teachers and their students at all levels. The Economics teachers' unpreparedness and inability to make the appropriate newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets available for use in the lesson periods makes their efforts abortive and unsuccessful, which could make learning less effective and might affect the student's academic performance in the school and any form of examination/evaluation.

Over the decades, many efforts were made to provide and distribute newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets by the Government, private organizations and other stakeholders to improve teaching and learning in schools. However, some teachers, especially Economics teachers, refused to utilize them to facilitate their instructions. Some still need to gain skills on using the available printed materials or making printed resources available through improvisation or any other means for classroom instruction. These were also reported by Okeke and Ezewulu (2021), who stated that these difficulties might be faced by Economics teachers at various schools in the state. This made teacher delivery more challenging and strenuous for both teachers and students. These were the major causes of ineffective teacher delivery and poor academic performance among students in Economics. These formed parts of the findings of Sirajo (2014), Yusuf (2015), and Usman (2016) in their various research works. However, there were serious problems with the poor State of Economics teaching and learning in most senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. This made researchers and stakeholders focus more on Economics Education in all the six educational zones of the State. Inappropriate utilization of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets during teaching delivery by Economics teachers may be one of the militating factors affecting students' academic performance in WAEC and other similar examinations in the state. Further, in 2014 WAEC, 25,331 students sat for WAEC in the 2013/2014 academic session in the State, but due to some of these problems, the State recorded only 7.12% passes (WAEC, 2014). This serious problem might be attributed to the need for more adequate and proper utilization of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets in lesson delivery.

Usman (2016) revealed that the unavailability of appropriate printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets in most Nigerian secondary schools made Economics teachers vulnerable to the

problems of poor performance. They usually complain that, the unavailability of printed instructional Materials in their teaching and learning processes will make students inactive and might lead to massive student failure and poor performance. This represented the most critical and alarming issue confronting the instruction and learning of Economics in our secondary schools, particularly in Sokoto State. The verbal presentation of Economics concepts to the learners, according to Yusuf (2018), led to problems which might include ineffective and inefficient teaching, slow rate of learning, poor performance in examinations, poor understanding, less interest in the subject and so on. These challenges posed significant obstacles to effective Economics Education in many of our schools. The Sokoto State Government should prioritize providing printed instructional materials to enhance the teaching and learning of Economics. Additional initiatives are required to evaluate, motivate, and ensure that teachers use printed resources in schools nationwide.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to:

1. To find out the impact of printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Research Question

The Research Question answered in this study was as follows:

1. What are the opinions of teachers and students on the impact of printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State?

Null Hypothesis

The study was guided by the following research hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Theoretical Framework: Constructivist Theory of Learning.

The constructivist learning theory, rooted in the studies of cognitive development by psychologists Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky, emerged as a foundation for understanding how thinking and knowledge evolve with age. Constructivism posits that children actively build knowledge through their engagement in learning activities. In a constructivist setting, learning is characterized by active participation, inquiry, problem-solving, and collaboration, with the teacher serving as a guide and facilitator rather than a mere dispenser of knowledge (Weegar and Pacis, 2012). In a constructivist classroom, students are provided with opportunities to develop profound understanding of materials, internalize knowledge, grasp the nature of knowledge development, and create intricate cognitive maps connecting various bodies of knowledge (Richardson, 2018). Olusegun (2015) emphasizes that teachers cannot simply transmit knowledge; students actively construct knowledge in their minds, discovering and transforming information and revising their understanding when necessary. The following are some benefits of the constructivist approach, as presented by Olusegun (2015 pp 3-7), include:

1. **Active Involvement:** Children learn more and enjoy learning when actively engaged rather than being passive listeners.
2. **Emphasis on Thinking and Understanding:** Education is most effective when it focuses on thinking and understanding rather than rote memorization.
3. **Transferability:** Constructivist learning promotes the transfer of knowledge.
4. **Student Ownership:** Constructivism gives students ownership of their learning.
5. **Real-World Context:** Constructivism stimulates and engages students by grounding activities in authentic, real-world contexts.
6. **Social and Communication Skills:** Constructivism fosters social and communication skills through a collaborative and idea-sharing classroom environment.

This theory was chosen for the current study due to its relevance to teaching and learning processes, aligning with the investigation into the impact of the availability and utilization of printed media resources on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. It helps teachers emphasize the relevant and important topics, encouraging students' critical thinking and group work by using various printed media resources that improve students' active participation in any teacher delivery. It also encourages students' active engagement in classroom activities, which helps them, explain and elaborate on what was learned. This is what prompted the choice of this theory in this work.

Methodology

Research Design

The research employed a descriptive research design, specifically utilizing a survey method. Descriptive research is apt for opinion-seeking studies, providing a blueprint for collecting data from a population to facilitate generalizations about the target group. The survey method, within this design, allows for the collection of opinions from a representative sample of the population and facilitating meaningful generalizations (Aliyu, 2016). As noted by Nmadi (2001), this design is particularly suitable as it offers a clear definition of the problem, meticulous data collection, careful analysis and interpretation, and skillful reporting of the findings.

Population of the Study

The population for this study comprised all Economics teachers and students in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. The Economics teachers' population was three hundred and sixty-one (361) across the six educational zones in the state. However, a total number of nineteen thousand, five hundred and ninety-eight (19,598) Senior Secondary School Two (SSII) Economics students from six educational zones were used. All from the one hundred and fourteen (114) Senior Secondary Schools that are offering Economics in the state served as the population of the study. Table 1 presented the population distribution of the schools offering Economics in Sokoto State, Economics teachers and SSII students for this study from the six Educational Zones.

Table1: Population breakdown by educational zones.

S/N	Educational Zones	No. of Senior Secondary schools	No. of SSII Students	No. of SSII Economics Teachers
1	Sokoto North	16	4,201	54
2	Sokoto South	27	3,134	84
3	Gwadabawa	15	1,849	47
4	Goronyo	23	3,818	72
5	Bodinga	15	3,197	48
6	Yabo	18	3,399	56
Total		114	19,598	361

Source: Sokoto State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, (2023)

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The total sample size of this study comprised three hundred and sixty-five (365) respondents sampled from Economics teachers and students in the study area as suggested by Research Advisor 2006 under 95% confidence (Dada, 2016). Multistage sampling techniques were employed in the selection of sampled schools, teachers and students. However, proportionate sampling procedure was used in selecting fifteen (15) schools out of thirty-one (31) schools of the two sampled educational zones as samples size. Eight (8) schools were sampled from Sokoto North educational zone, and Seven (7) from Bodinga educational zones. Furthermore, fifty-one (51) Economics teachers were sampled from the total number of one hundred and two (102) SSII Economics teachers of the two sampled educational zones of the state. Both sampled schools and teachers were chosen by assigning numbers to all the schools and teachers of the sampled zones; then, all the even numbers were taken as the sample size. Two (2) educational zones were sampled out of Six Educational Zones in Sokoto State. These zones were sampled using balloting sampling technique. The names of the zones were written on pieces of papers, folded, put in a container and were mixed thoroughly. The SSII Economics students were asked to pick out the folded papers (through lucky dip) containing the names of the zones from the same container without replacement.

Table 2: Respondents Distribution of the two sampled Educational Zones.

Zone	Educational Zones	Sampled Secondary Schools	Sampled Economics Students	Sampled Economics Teachers	Sampled Econs Teachers and Students
B	Sokoto North	8	163	27	190
E	Bodinga	7	151	24	175
Total		15	314	51	365

Source: Sokoto State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, (2023)

Instrumentation

The instrument used for this study was researchers designed questionnaire for both teachers and students. It was titled “Questionnaire for Economics Teachers and Students (QETS). This questionnaire was used by the researchers for the collection of data from the respondents at various schools. It contained twelve (12) items which required respondents’ responses. Further, this questionnaire was also designed using a four (4) modified Points Likert Scale using Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The respondents were required to tick in the appropriate box. It also contained items related to all the research questions set for the study which provided required answers.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument used for this study was subjected to face, content and construct validation by research experts in the fields of Economics (to check the content), English language (to check language and grammatical constructions) and from measurement and evaluation Section (to check the design and statistical tools for analysis) from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The validity of any research instrument is the ability of that instrument to measure thoroughly and accurately the purpose for which it was constructed for. Therefore, the subjection of this instrument to the experts was to ensure its validity and measure what it intended to measure. The observations and suggestions of these experts were incorporated in the final draft of the instrument.

Pilot Testing

The researchers carried out a pilot test at Government Day Secondary School, Dingyadi in Bodinga educational zone of Sokoto state. The test was conducted in the school which was not part of the sample size. The researchers and their assistants took permission from the Head of the school before the distribution of the instrument to the respondents. Thirty (30) copies of the instrument were administered to five teachers and twenty-five students in the pilot school where they were asked to express their views and response to all the items by choosing one out of the multiple responses provided. The instrument was distributed, retrieved, scored and analyzed. The result revealed 0.85 Reliability Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance. The result of methodological pilot test was computed using Cronbach’s Alpha to determine the Reliability Coefficient of the pilot test.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability coefficient of the instrument was assessed following a successful pilot test conducted with thirty (30) copies of the instrument from the pilot school. The Test–Retest reliability method was employed, and the results were analyzed using Cronbach’s Alpha. The obtained Cronbach’s Alpha value was 0.85, which was in proximity to one (1). According to Usman (2016), the closer the result is to a positive one (1), the more reliable the instruments are considered. Additionally, Balogun (2000) in Sirajo (2014) stated that any reliability index ranging from 0.5 and above can be deemed high enough for use in real research. Therefore, the instrument used demonstrated high reliability and consistency for the intended study, as the result was close to one. This justifies the use of the instrument.

Procedures for Data Collection

The research was set by taking an introductory letter obtained from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria to all the Principals of the sampled schools to solicit permission to use their Economics teachers and students in the collection of data for the study. The researchers were assisted by research assistants (Economics teachers in the visited schools) in administering the instruments to the students in their various classes. One day (2 hours) training was given to two Economics teachers in all the schools visited. The training was aimed at giving them the awareness of what they were expected to do, their boundaries and how to retrieve the copies of the instrument administered without having any problem or challenge. Further, the teachers’ questionnaire was administered to them (by self) in their staff rooms. The researchers explained to all the respondents on how to respond to all the items on the questionnaire. This assisted the researchers to collect the first-hand information for this study. However, the researchers got one hundred percent (100%) return rate for all the instrument administered. This was because more trained hands were involved in sharing and retrieving the instrument from the students and teachers. This enabled the researchers to collect necessary information on the Impact of availability and utilization of printed instructional materials on teacher delivery in Economics in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State from all the sampled schools.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The collected data were meticulously organized and classified by the researchers. The analysis of the Research Questions involved the use of simple percentages, frequency tables, and descriptive statistics, including the Mean and Standard Deviation. Additionally, non-parametric statistics, specifically the Mann-Whitney U-Test, was employed to test all the five null hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance.

Results

The responses gathered from the research question was meticulously subjected to statistical measures, specifically Mean and Standard Deviation, to answer the research question formulated for this study.

Research Question One: What are the opinions of teachers and students on the impact of printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State? In order to answer this research question, the data collected on the impact of newspaper, magazine, journal, article, periodicals and pamphlet on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State was analysed using Mean and Standard Deviation. The outcomes of this analysis are succinctly summarized in Table 3 as follows:

Table 3 Mean and Standard Deviation on the opinions of Respondents on the Impact of Newspaper, Magazine, Journal, Articles, Periodical, and Pamphlets on Teacher Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

S/ No	Item statements	Category of Respondents	Population	Mean	Decision rule
1.	The use of Newspapers in teaching and learning of Economics was very effective and relevant.	Teachers	51	3.5	Accepted
		Students	314	3.1	Accepted
2.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use Newspapers in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	3.2	Accepted
		Students	314	3.1	Accepted
3.	The use of Magazines by Economics teachers in teaching and learning of Economics was very efficient and productive.	Teachers	51	3.0	Accepted
		Students	314	2.8	Accepted
4.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use Magazines in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	2.7	Accepted
		Students	314	2.8	Accepted
5.	The Journals were professionally chosen and used by Economics teachers in my school for effective teacher delivery.	Teachers	51	3.8	Accepted
		Students	314	3.1	Accepted
6.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use Journals in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	3.6	Accepted
		Students	314	3.2	Accepted
7.	Articles were adequately used by Economics teachers in teaching and learning of Economics in my school.	Teachers	51	2.6	Accepted
		Students	314	2.8	Accepted
8.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use articles in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	3.9	Accepted
		Students	314	3.7	Accepted
9.	The use of Periodicals in teaching and learning of Economics was very interesting and informative.	Teachers	51	2.5	Accepted
		Students	314	2.8	Accepted
10.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use periodicals in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	2.8	Accepted
		Students	314	2.9	Accepted
11.	The use of Pamphlets in teaching and learning of Economics was very effective and efficient.	Teachers	51	3.1	Accepted
		Students	314	3.0	Accepted
12.	Teachers and Students find it difficult to use Pamphlets in teaching and learning of Economics.	Teachers	51	3.3	Accepted
		Students	314	3.1	Accepted
Cumulative Mean				3.5	

Source: Field work

Note. Table three presents the analysis of respondents' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. The cumulative mean was 3.5, which is greater than the 2.5 benchmark. Based on this, the decision rule revealed that, all items were accepted. This also implied that, teachers and students agreed with all the items, with a mean of each item above 2.5, which means that all the items were agreed upon and retained. The analysis showed that teachers and students agreed that newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Hypotheses Testing

The following is the null hypothesis formulated for this study and tested as follows:

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. To test the null hypothesis one, Mann-Whitney (U-test) statistic was used. The summary of the analysis is presented in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4: Summary of Mann-Whitney test Analysis on the opinions between Students and Teachers on the Impact of Newspaper, Magazine, Journal, Articles, Periodicals and Pamphlets on Teacher's Delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	χ^2	Df	p-value	Decision
Teachers	51	218.51	10925.50	2.635	362	0.321	Retained
Students	314	176.77	55504.50				

Significant at level of ≤ 0.05

Table 4 presents the Mann-Whitney (U-test) analysis result equal to 2.635 and the P-value equal to 0.321. The calculated P-value of 0.321 is greater than the alpha value 0.05 ($P = 0.321 > 0.05$). This implies that, there is no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. Hence the null hypothesis which said, There is no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State was retained. Moreover, the outcomes also revealed that newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

Summary of Finding

Based on the study, the following findings were made: Newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets have impact on teachers' Economics delivery among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, and there is no significant difference between teachers and students regarding this ($P = 0.321$).

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings was systematically done by aligning research question with the corresponding null hypothesis as follows:

Research question one: What are the opinions of teachers and students on the impact of printed media resources such as newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State? In answering this question, the analysis revealed that, teachers and students agreed that using newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. All items were accepted because the cumulative mean was 3.5, which was greater than the 2.5 benchmark. As a result, **the null hypothesis one**, which said that there was no significant difference between teachers' and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals, and pamphlets on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State was retained and hence conclude that there was no significant difference between teachers and students' opinions on the impact of newspapers, magazine, journal, articles, periodical, and pamphlets on teacher delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. Furthermore, the result also revealed that newspapers, magazines, journals, articles, periodicals and pamphlets have impact on teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.

In support of these findings, Adogboji and Toyo's (2006) research disclosed that, various types of print media that improve and enhance academic performance of students include: Newspapers, magazines, banners, textbooks, fliers, billboard, circulars, journals, pamphlets, periodicals and others not covered in their studies, significantly contribute to improving and enhancing students' academic performance. However, Ikpesu and Nkem's (2021) findings revealed that instructional materials are very important factors in teaching and effective teaching cannot take place without the availability and utilization of basic relevant instructional materials. The result also aligned with the observations of Tety (2016), who emphasized that, teachers consider instructional materials as key to academic performance. This implied that the Schools with inadequacy of printed

media resources and instructors are likely to perform low whereas schools with adequate printed instructional materials and instructors are likely to perform high.

This discovery did not align with the research conducted by Usman (2016) who reported that, there was a significant difference in the opinions of the respondents on the availability of instructional materials and students' academic performance in Economics in senior secondary schools. The finding was also not consistent with Ahmed's study in 2019 which revealed that, there was a significant difference between the impact of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of Economics in senior secondary schools. Additionally, Dahiru, Akinpade and Aluko's (2021), findings also revealed that, instructional facilities were inadequate and the available of instructional facilities were not fully utilized in teachings Agricultural science. Also, the finding was not in line with finding of Ehirim, Iwuchukwu and Okenyi (2020), asserting that, many instructional materials were available, but they were not adequately utilized and chemistry teachers do not appropriately improvise instructional materials when not available in the teaching and learning of chemistry. These findings underscore the crucial role of instructional materials in influencing students' academic performance across various educational settings and geographical locations in the state.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the availability and utilization of printed media resources have impact on teacher delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. It was also concluded that, teachers who are skillful in selecting and utilizing printed media resources deliver well in Economics among Secondary schools. It could be generalized as a conclusion that, the availability and utilization of printed media resources in teacher delivery alone do not bring about effectiveness and efficiency unless such printed materials are accessible, affordable by the school teachers and easily improvisable by the teachers and students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, it was recommended that:

1. The school management should provide printed media resources to be used by the Economics teacher for proper teacher's delivery in Economics among Secondary Schools in Sokoto State.
2. The state Ministry of Education, school management, teachers, parents, NGOs, and philanthropies should always make printed media resources available for teachers to use for proper teacher's delivery in Economics.
3. Economics teachers should encourage their students to bring any relevant printed materials to school for use, storage, retrieval, and re-use for proper teacher's delivery in Economics among secondary schools in Sokoto State.
4. School management should organize relevant workshops, training and re-training of Economics teachers on how to improvise and utilize such printed media resources.

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